

THE POLITICAL ROLE OF THE ASHTARKHANIS IN THE HISTORY OF BUKHARA

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Introduction: The Ashtarkhanis were a powerful dynasty in Bukhara, tracing their roots back to the influential Shaybanid tribe. Under the leadership of Abdullah Khan II, the Ashtarkhanis established themselves as the ruling family of Bukhara in the 18th century. The Ashtarkhanis played a significant role in shaping the political landscape of Bukhara, leaving behind a legacy of cultural and architectural achievements.

The Ashtarkhanis rose to power in Bukhara in the late 15th century, establishing a dynasty that ruled for over 200 years. Under the leadership of Ashtarkhani rulers such as Abdullah Khan II, the dynasty expanded its influence through military conquests and political alliances. The Ashtarkhanis played a significant role in shaping the political landscape and cultural development of Bukhara, leaving a lasting legacy. The Ashtarkhanid dynasty lasted until 1756. The dynasty consisted of eight khans: 1. Baqi Muhammad (1601-1605), 2. His brother Vali Muhammad Khan (1605-1611), 3. Imam Quli Khan (1611-1642), 4. His brother Nadir Muhammad Khan (1642-1645), 5. His son Abdulaziz -khan (1645-1681), 6. His brother Subkhanqulikhan (1681-1702). 7. His son Ubaydullah Khan (1702-1711), 8. His brother Abul-fayzkhan (1711-1747). Only three of them ended their lives on the throne. Three of them (Vali Muhammad, Ubaidullah, Abulfaiz Khan) were tragically killed as a result of palace coups. Two of them spent their lives in exile after being overthrown. The main reason for all of this is that during the Ashtar Khan Uzbek dynasties, the struggle for power and the throne, even between fathers and children, brothers and relatives, intensified to an unprecedented level.

The line of the Ashtarkhanid dynasty reaches Genghis Khan and is the 13th son of Joji Khan. Tokai dates back to Timur. Jozhikhan's eldest son Botukhon Tokai gave 14 uluses to Temur, more precisely, Mangishloq, Haji Tarkhan and the lands in the North Caucasus were given as property. Below is "Shajarayi Turk" by Abulghazi Bahadirkhan of Ashtarkhani, by Abdurahman Tolen "Tarihi Abulfayzkhan", "Silsilat as-Salatin" by Haji Mir Muhammad Salim, Marjani Genealogy based on the works of Shahabeddin "Mustafad al-akhbar fi ahvali

Kazan and Bulgar" nations are listed. Also in the table is Abdusattar Jumanazar by Abdul Qadir ibn Based on the work "Majma' al-Ansab wa-l-Ashjam" by Muhammad Amin, but in the work Precisely because there are places where the genealogies of Shaibani and Ashtarkhani are confused. There is no extract from the work and the information in the work is compared with other sources an identified genealogical loop is also provided. A branch of the Tokai-Temuri dynasty The state of migration and settlement in Turon has been a special "white spot" in history for many years. came[4]. Historians say that this situation happened after Ivan IV Grozny conquered Ashtarkhan Khanate was considered to have been implemented. This migration is the result of research by scientists It was found that it took place long before the fall of the Ashtar Khan Khanate. Mahmud ibn Wali's work Bahr ul-asrar to the Shaibani family of Tokai-Timuri the state of migration and their first arrival in Turon is discussed. This is the case it is assumed not to be found in any other historical source. Interior of the Ashtarkhan Khanate conflicts and power struggles in the Nogai Horde under the leadership of Mangishlaq Khan He encouraged a branch of the Tokai-Temuri dynasty to move to Turon. According to Bahr ulasar, Magishlaq Khan first went to the city of Tura to Kuchum Khan and that from there he went to Husayn Boygaro. Timurid sultan warmly welcomed him, Magishlaq Khan gave 12,000 soldiers to recapture the lands he considered his own. Lower Because the military campaign to Volgaboyi and Mangishlaq ended ineffectually then the khan had to return to Turon. Mangishlaq Khan according to Mahmud ibn Wali In Turan, Shaybani Jonibek was involved in the upbringing of the sultan's descendants, here He died in 1528 and was buried in Miyanqal.

The Ashtarkhanis established themselves as rulers of Bukhara in the mid-16th century, consolidating power through strategic alliances. The Ashtarkhanis commissioned the construction of iconic structures in Bukhara, such as the Kalyan Minaret and the Ark Fortress. Under Ashtarkhani rule, Bukhara became a center for arts and learning, attracting scholars, poets, and artisans from across the region. The Ashtarkhani dynasty faced challenges from external invasions and internal strife, leading to their eventual decline and fall from power. The Ashtarkhani dynasty was founded by Ashtarkhan, who established a powerful and influential lineage in Bukhara. Notable rulers of the Ashtarkhani dynasty. Ibrahim Ashtarkhani was a prominent ruler known for his military conquests and efforts to expand the dynasty's territory. The Ashtarkhanis implemented land redistribution programs, introduced new irrigation techniques, and promoted the cultivation of cash crops. They established trade

routes, built markets, and encouraged the growth of the silk and spice trade, boosting the economy of Bukhara. The Ashtarkhanis imposed taxes on goods, services, and land to fund public projects, maintain infrastructure, and support the military.

The Ashtarkhanis commissioned stunning mosques and palaces, such as the Char Minar and the Ark Fortress, showcasing intricate tilework and grand designs. Ashtarkhani rulers patronized renowned poets and scholars, fostering a rich literary tradition that produced works like the Divan-i Hafiz and Baburnama. The Ashtarkhanis supported talented artists and craftsmen, leading to the creation of exquisite miniatures, intricate textiles, and vibrant ceramics.

The Ashtarkhanis promoted art, architecture, and literature, leaving behind a rich cultural heritage in Bukhara. They implemented administrative changes, such as tax reforms and infrastructure improvements, shaping the governance of Bukhara. The Ashtarkhanis fostered trade and commerce, establishing Bukhara as a thriving economic center in Central Asia. The Ashtarkhani dynasty faced internal disputes over succession, weakening their hold on power and leading to instability within the ruling family. The dynasty was threatened by external invasions from neighboring regions, such as the Timurids and the Shaybanids, which further weakened their control over Bukhara. Economic mismanagement and declining revenues from trade routes contributed to the dynasty's decline, leading to financial instability and loss of support from the merchant class.

The Ashtarkhanis significantly expanded Bukhara's territory through conquests and strategic alliances with neighboring regions. Their rule left a lasting impact on Bukhara's culture and architecture, with the construction of impressive monuments and palaces. The Ashtarkhanis established a stable political system and efficient administrative structure that endured for centuries in Bukhara. The Ashtarkhanis, like the Mughals, wielded significant political power, controlling vast territories and maintaining centralized rule. In contrast to the Timurids, the Ashtarkhanis had a more limited cultural influence, focusing primarily on political and military expansion. Compared to the Safavids, the Ashtarkhanis left a lasting impact on Bukhara's political landscape, shaping its governance and administration for centuries.

Conclusion: The Ashtarkhanis left a lasting impact on Bukhara's political landscape, shaping its governance and administration for centuries. Their rule extended beyond Bukhara, influencing neighboring regions and fostering cultural and political exchange in Central Asia. The Ashtarkhanis established a

hereditary lineage of rulers, ensuring stability and continuity in Bukhara's political leadership. Even after their eventual decline, the Ashtarkhanis remain a significant chapter in Bukhara's history, shaping its identity and political traditions.

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